

Our commentary on forest protection and carbon credits trade

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Our latest contribution to the world's battle against climate and biodiversity crises was an expert commentary on Vietnamese forests and the prospect of carbon credits trade. The article appeared in the *Land and Climate Review* on Feb. 2, 2024 [1].

In the current context of Vietnam, the approach can be considered a promising (bold) step forward as far as the “eco-surplus culture” pursuit is concerned [2]. Apparently, there exist risks and uncertainties when it comes to real-world implementation, but no risk can compare to the “doing nothing” one.

This newest commentary represents our genuine attempt to draw the world's attention to long-standing problems and challenges in protecting natural resources in developing regions, which may help mitigate the worsening of an eco-deficit culture [3].

References

- [1] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Forests of gold: carbon credits could be game-changing for Vietnam. <https://www.landclimate.org/forests-of-gold-carbon-credits-could-be-game-changing-for-vietnam/>
- [2] Vuong QH. (2021). The semiconducting principle of monetary and environmental values exchange. *Economics and Business Letters*, 10(3), 284-290. <https://doi.org/10.17811/ebl.10.3.2021.284-290>
- [3] Vuong QH. (2021). Western monopoly of climate science is creating an eco-deficit culture. <https://www.landclimate.org/western-monopoly-of-climate-science-is-creating-an-eco-deficit-culture/>

